

Yoda

research data management

WAGENINGEN
UNIVERSITY & RESEARCH

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Guidance summary for data package curation in Yoda@WUR v01

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Based on: (summary of) yoda_curation_guidance_20240621_v01.pdf

Summary curation guidelines for data packages in Yoda@WUR

- ❖ This document is a summary of the Yoda@WUR curation guidance document. This summary can serve as a checklist for data package submitters and Yoda@WUR data managers that are familiar with Yoda@WUR data package curation.
- ❖ Please see the document 'yoda_curation_guidance_[date]_[version].pdf' if you are not familiar or experienced with data package curation in Yoda@WUR.
- ❖ Please contact data@wur.nl for questions or curation support / advice by data librarians at the WUR Library.

1 Archiving data packages in the Yoda@WUR vault checklist

1.1 Rightsholder.

- No indications that the data package is not allowed to be deposited
- Rightsholder(s) and, when applicable, special regulations are documented.

1.2 Creator(s).

- The submitter is (one of) the creator(s) of the data package.
- Yoda metadata fields are filled in: 'funder', 'award number', 'creator(s)' and 'affiliation', 'contributor(s)' and 'affiliation(s)'. Preferably, persistent identifiers are used for any affiliations.
- All creators and contributors to the data package are filled in.

1.3 Reused materials.

- The Yoda metadata field 'description' indicates whether reused materials are present or referred to within files.
- The Yoda metadata fields under 'related resource' are filled in ('relation type', 'title', 'persistent identifier').
- Any reused materials usage and methods are documented in the readme file or codebook.
- Already published reused materials are not present (unless valid reasons dictate otherwise).

1.4 Sensitive information.

- When applicable, (personal) sensitive information is separated from pseudonymised or otherwise non-sensitive information and submitted separately to the vault.

1.5 Contact address.

- The readme file presents (a) contact address(es).
- At least one of the contact addresses is managed by multiple people.

1.6 Retention period.

- The Yoda metadata field 'retention period' is filled in.
- Retention period takes into account the GDPR principles.
- Retention period does not violate any contracts or informed consents.
- Retention period is in line with policies.

1.7 Expiration retention period.

- The Yoda metadata field 'retention information' and / or readme file specifies what to do after retention period.

1.8 Readme file.

- The data package is clearly documented in a readme file (preferably according to the WUR documentation templates), which is filled in completely.
- Scripts and code are clearly documented.
- Elaborate documentation on manual processing steps of the data is present in the readme.

1.9 Yoda metadata form.

- Yoda metadata is filled in correctly and completely where applicable.
- Preferably, persistent identifiers for creators and contributors are present.

1.10 Missing files and folders.

- There are no missing files or folder (discerned from documentation and purpose of research).

1.11 Formats used.

- Non-preferred formats are converted to preferred formats.
- Unconverted non-preferred formats are sufficiently documented.

1.12 Folder and filenames.

- Folder and file naming is logical and consistent.
- File and folder names are as independent as possible from its location.
- Folder and filenames are concise and descriptive.
- Abbreviations are documented.
- Special characters are not used.
- Dashes and underscores are used instead of white spaces or periods.
- Lower capitals are applied as much as possible.
- Versioning is applied consistently where applicable.

1.13 Folder structure.

- Folder structure is logical.
- Mixing of file / data contents in one folder is avoided or makes sense.
- Folder structure is not deeper than 5 folders (unless reasons dictate otherwise).
- Folder structure is not too shallow.
- Raw data and processed data are in separate folders.

1.14 Software required.

- Required software is documented.
- Dependencies to use software, libraries, or packages are documented.

1.15 Hidden or temporary files

- No temporary files present (.temp, .tmp, files starting with ~\$).
- No desktop.ini files present.
- No Indexing files present (Apple ._, DS_Store, etc).
- No history files present (for example .Rhistory).

1.16 Readability.

- All files or a selection of files can be opened.
- Files are not corrupted.
- There are no duplicate folders and files.

1.17 Common practices.

- Files are (also) presented in preferred formats.
- Files adhere to common data science practices.

2 Publishing from the Yoda@WUR vault check list

2.1 Sensitive information

- There is no sensitive information present for open access publications.
- Sensitive information is separated as much as possible from non-sensitive information.
- If sensitive information present, Yoda metadata field 'data package access' is set to either restricted or closed when there is no agreement allowing open publication.

2.2 Licence

- A proper 'Open Access' license is chosen (preferably CC BY) if allowed.
- If license is set to 'Custom' a 'license.txt' is present in the parent folder of the data package stating terms of use (or limitations thereof).

2.3 Contractual obligations

- There are no contractual obligations limiting publication.

2.4 Reused materials

- Existing published reused materials are not present (unless reasons dictate otherwise).
- For any type of reused material, the submitter acknowledges to adhere to their terms of use / licenses.

2.5 Creator(s).

- All creators and contributors are present.
- The submitter is allowed to publish.

2.6 Value creation

- If a [Data & Software Disclosure Form \(DSDF\)](#) is not present, the submitter is made aware of possible value creation.

- The chair or business unit manager agrees to publication.